

STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART XIV. THE FRIES ISOMERISATION OF ACYL ESTERS OF *o*- AND *p*-HYDROXY-ACETOPHENONES AND *p*-HYDROXYBENZOPHENONE

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Fries isomerisation of acyl esters of *o*- and *p*-hydroxy-acetophenones to 2-hydroxy-5-acetylacetophenone and acyl and benzoyl esters of 2-hydroxybenzophenone to 3-acetyl- and 3-benzoyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone respectively has been effected.

The Fries migration of a number of negatively substituted phenolic esters has been investigated in recent years (Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 873; Shah and Shah, *this Journal*, 1949, **26**, 237; Amin and Shah, *ibid.*, 1952, **29**, 351, 915; *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, **21**, 246; Chaughuley and Amin, *Science & Culture*, 1954, **19**, 614), but the information regarding the migration of acyl esters of hydroxyacetophenones and benzophenones appears to be scanty (Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, **460**, 56). In the present investigation therefore, the Fries isomerisation of *o*- and *p*-acetoxy-acetophenones and *p*-acetoxybenzophenone has been investigated. Treatment of *o*-acetoxy-acetophenone with anhydrous aluminium chloride at temperatures ranging from 120° to 170° yielded only a pasty mass, but on carrying out this reaction in nitrobenzene as a solvent at room temperature, a diketone of m.p. 93-94° was obtained. *p*-Acetoxy-acetophenone on similar treatment furnished only the deacetylated product, but on heating this compound with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 140°-150° in absence of a solvent, the diketone of m.p. 93-94°, identical with the previous one, was obtained. This diketone has been assigned the constitution, 2-hydroxy-5-acetylacetophenone as:

(i) In the first case the migration took place at room temperature. It is more likely that the acetyl group has migrated to *para* position with respect to OH group. (ii) In the case of *p*-acetoxyacetophenone, the migration can only take place in the *ortho* position, the *para* position being occupied. This diketone responds to Pyman's test, showing the presence of ketonic group in the *ortho* position. (iii) Both the diketones on methylation and subsequent oxidation by alkaline permanganate yield 1-methoxyisophthalic acid, m.p. 261° (Schall, *Ber.*, 1879, **12**, 828; Stoermer and Behn, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 2458).

The migration of acetyl and benzoyl esters of *p*-hydroxybenzophenone was similarly carried out at 160°-165° without a solvent, 3-acetyl- and 3-benzoyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone respectively being obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Fries Migration of o- and p-Acetoxyacetophenones: Formation of 2-Hydroxy-5-acetylacetophenone.—(i). *o*-Acetoxyacetophenone, prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method, crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 88-89°. Friedländer and Neudorfer (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1080) report the same melting point.

To aluminium chloride (7.5 g., 3.3 *M*), dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (30 c.c.), *o*-acetoxyacetophenone (3 g., 1 *M*.) was added gradually with stirring and cooling under tap. It was left overnight at room temperature (CaCl₂ guard-tube) and then treated with crushed ice and HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) and steam-distilled. The hot residual liquid was filtered off to remove some tarry matter; the filtrate on cooling deposited white lustrous needles, which were collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 92-93°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 5.4. C₁₀H₁₀O₃ requires C, 67.4; H, 5.6 per cent).

(ii). *p*-Acetoxyacetophenone, prepared as before, crystallised from hot water containing a little alcohol in flat needles, m.p. 54-55°. Verley (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1898, iii, 19, 140) reports m.p. 54°.

An intimate mixture of *p*-acetoxyacetophenone (3 g., 1.1 *M*.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (7.5 g., 3.3 *M*.) was heated at 140°-150° for an hour (CaCl₂ guard-tube) when HCl fumes copiously evolved. On decomposing the cold reaction mixture with ice and HCl (conc.), a solid separated which was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles, m.p. 92-93°, yield 1.2 g. (mixed m.p. with the migration product of *o*-acetoxyacetophenone being undepressed).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from dilute alcohol in reddish needles, m.p. 189-90°. (Found: N, 20.65. C₂₂H₁₇O₆N₈ requires N, 20.85 per cent).

The methyl ether, prepared by dimethyl sulphate-potassium carbonate-acetone method, crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 86°. (Found: C, 68.55; H, 6.40. C₁₁H₁₂O₃ requires 68.75; H, 6.25 per cent).

Fries Migration of p-Acetoxybenzophenone: Formation of 3-Acetyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone.—*p*-Acetoxybenzophenone, prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method, crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 81-82°. Döbner and Stackmann (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1970) report the same melting point.

An intimate mixture of *p*-acetoxybenzophenone (3 g., 1 *M*.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.5 g., 3.3 *M*) was heated at 150°-160° for about an hour (CaCl₂ guard-tube). On working it up, the product crystallised from dilute acetic acid in rhombic prisms, m.p. 102-103°. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 4.9. C₁₄H₁₂O₃ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0 per cent). It develops a violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in alkali with a yellow colour.

The semicarbazone, prepared as usual, crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 249-50° (decomp.). (Found N, 23.6. C₁₇H₁₇O₃N₃ requires N, 23.8 per cent).

The methoxy derivative, prepared by dimethyl sulphate-alkali method, crystallised from alcohol in tiny flat needles, m.p. 108-109°. (Found: C, 75.5. H, 5.4. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5 per cent).

Fries Migration of p-Benzoyloxybenzophenone : Formation of 3-Benzoyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone.—The *p*-benzoyloxybenzophenone, prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, crystallised from alcohol in lustrous needles, m.p. 112°.

p-Benzoyloxybenzophenone (3 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.5 g., 3.3 *M*) were intimately mixed and heated at 160°-165° for an hour (CaCl₂ guard-tube). On working up the product as before, the substance obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in tiny needles, m.p. 105-106°. Pieroni (*Gazzetta*, 1932, 62, 387) reports the same m.p.

The *benzoyloxy derivative*, prepared as before, crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 144-45°. (Found : C, 83.0 ; H, 4.0. C₂₇H₁₈O₄ requires C, 83.2 ; H, 3.7 per cent).

The *oxime*, prepared as usual, crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 214° (decomp.). (Found : N, 13.0. C₂₀H₁₆O₃N₂ requires N, 13.2 per cent).

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